

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: KUSEMERERWA****FIRST NAME: DONNA****PROGRAM CODE: PHGH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author did did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 10)

Key Concepts

1. Style guide (EUCLID 2019, 24- 25)
2. Personal examples and academic style (EUCLID 2019, 12)
3. Writing rules of thumb (EUCLID 2019, 5- 13)
4. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2019, 5- 13)
5. Quotations and quotation marks (EUCLID 2019, 6- 7, 15- 17, 19, 35, 47)
6. American vs British English (EUCLID 2019, 27- 34)
7. Citations and referencing ((EUCLID 2019, 4, 6, 10-12, 24)

FOOD FOR THE DOCTORAL JOURNEY

1) INTRODUCTION

The coursepack provided for period one of the international academic writing for doctoral students' course (EUCLID 2019) covers a wide range of topics intended to give students an overview of information and knowledge vital for the journey which culminates in the writing of a doctoral thesis. The topics that caught my attention at first glance were plagiarism and use of style. The former because of my fascination with the topic which I only heard about after obtained my Bachelor's degree in the mid-nineties. And the latter because I still struggle with style almost thirty years since I first graduated.

The first chapter of the study material is guidance on essay writing. Using material from a University of New South Wales Guide reproduced with permission (EUCLID 2019, 1- 4), the reader is given tips on researching a topic, writing, referencing and editing an essay. The study guide then goes on to cover topics ranging from rules of thumb for writing to the use of Latin abbreviations and expressions. The coursepack is accompanied by a video which I was unable to use because of its lack of sound.

In this paper I will explore seven issues that appeal to me either because I need to deepen my understanding of the particular subject matter or because I find the topics

interesting. I consider this exploration akin to that special food that one takes before embarking on what is likely to be a long arduous journey without knowing when the next meal will come and how palatable it will be.

2) STYLE GUIDE

A style guide is described as, “a means of documenting your approach as a writer to certain elements of writing which need to be consistent” (EUCLID 2019, 24). The style that a writer adopts depends on the nature of the material being written and to some extent on the target audience. The study guide identifies forms of writing such as technical, journalism as well as commercial writing. The course for which this paper is being written is aptly titled academic writing given its focus on equipping the students for a rigorous academic program that hinges on correct scientific writing.

I have had to write a lot in my lifetime both as a student and as a professional but have so far failed to develop a distinct personal style for my documents. I actually find the whole idea of style quite intimidating. The study guide lists at least fifteen aspects of style including font usage, manuscript layout, structure, spelling and branding (EUCLID 2019, 24-25). One of the consultancy firms I have worked for in the past has a fourteen-page style guide for its consultants to use. It gives specific guidance on all the fifteen aspects of style that are listed in our guide and goes further to detail things like color palettes for each section of each report and the types of pictures that can be used. It is very helpful that EUCLID also pays a lot of attention to style providing templates for all papers required of students in order to ensure consistent, standardized and uniform outputs.

3) PERONAL EXAMPLES AND ACADEMIC STYLE

One of the things that struck me in the sections on style was the idea that personal examples may be used in academic writing (EUCLID 2019, 12). Given that the study material did not elaborate much on this point, I sought first to confirm what academic writing was and not make any assumptions. According to Leeds University, characteristics of academic writing are that it is:

Planned and focused: answers the question and demonstrates an understanding of the subject.

Structured: is coherent, written in a logical order, and brings together related points and material.

Evidenced: demonstrates knowledge of the subject area, supports opinions and arguments with evidence, and is referenced accurately.

Formal in tone and style: uses appropriate language and tenses, and is clear, concise and balanced.

The characteristics left me wondering what personal examples could fit in such a framework for an academic paper on health systems for example. I was unable to answer this question and decided to defer it to some future time when I could consult one of the lecturers or someone else knowledgeable on the matter.

Another piece of advice that caught my attention in this section on academic style was the warning never to use contractions (ibid.). As a mother, the word contractions conjures up images of labor wards and I wondered if the word had not been used incorrectly. To my surprise the second definition of contraction in the Merriam Webster Online Dictionary is, “a shortening of a word syllable or word group by omission of a sound or letter; a form produced by such shortening’ (Merriam Webster n.d). The contractions that we are exhorted not to use in our writing include can’t, won’t and isn’t. I use these words continually in my day to day conversations but I would not have been able to use the noun contraction, to collectively describe them. A vivid reminder of the old adage, learning never ends.

4) RULES OF THUMB FOR WRITING

An entire chapter of the study material is dedicated to equipping us with rules of thumb for writing papers. According to the authors, the central idea of any paper must be succinctly presented as early as possible (EUCLID 2019, 14). They go on to urge writers not to make sweeping statements but rather to write clearly, simply using an interesting style. I found it rather disconcerting that without any preamble the chapter delves into John Rawls’ difference principle (ibid.). Although it is presented as an example under the guidance to keep writing focused, I feel that the authors themselves did not. The example is tailored to an audience who know who John Rawls is and why the study of his works is important. Prior to picking up the study guide I had never heard of John Rawls. As a credit to the authors their example prompted me to find out that John Rawls was one of the leading moral and political philosophers of the twentieth century (Richardson n.d.). One of his seminal works is titled *A Theory of Justice*, in which he describes the difference principle of distributive justice that addresses social and economic inequalities in society (Barata 2019). In the end I was happy to learn something new completely outside the academic subject areas that I am used to. I also learnt some new words (EUCLID 2019, 15), neologisms which Merriam Webster defines as, “a new word, usage or expression” and *polysyllabophilia* which is not listed in the Merriam Webster Dictionary. The other rules discussed include the need to support assertions and avoid plagiarism. I intend to put the rule about reading all writing out loud into practice on completion of this paper. According to the authors writing that sounds right, reads right (EUCLID 2019, 16).

5) PLAGIARISM

The coursepack states that plagiarism is when a writer, “uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information” (EUCLID 2019, 5). The study guide goes further to state that plagiarism is an unacceptable academic

offence to be avoided at all costs. The consequences of the offence can be severe even leading to the cancellation of a degree. I do not recall that during my undergraduate program the idea or concept of plagiarism was ever mentioned even though the word has been used in English to refer to the theft of ideas since the early seventeenth century (Bailey 2019). In graduate school we were taught that the mere thought of failing to acknowledge use of another person's ideas was to be abhorred. Given that I entered graduate school just over a year after leaving Makerere University where I did my first degree, it was disappointing that my *alma mater* did not make students aware about a concept so central to academic pursuit.

The study guide has a section on how to avoid plagiarism that emphasizes correct citation of sources of information, discusses the use of quotations and describes how to properly paraphrase another author's work (EUCLID 2019, 6-8). However, I feel that the chapter falls short of fully equipping a student like me who may be returning to school after many years of absence. In addition, many who completed their degrees in lowly ranked universities in less well-resourced countries, may not fully appreciate what does or does not constitute plagiarism and would perhaps benefit from specific examples from EUCLID of what has judged to be plagiarism. In my opinion the chapter also ought to have introduced readers to the use of anti-plagiarism software which is now in common use.

It was helpful to be reminded that not all information has to be cited (EUCLID 2019, 10). When information is common knowledge no citation need be given. I would submit that the methods to prevent the spread of COVID-19 provide a good illustration for this in the current times. I can authoritatively say that frequent hand washing, social distancing and wearing a mask in public will protect individuals and communities from the scourge of the SARS-CoV-2 virus without being accused of plagiarism.

6) AMERICAN VS BRITISH ENGLISH

I was rather surprised to find that a full chapter was reserved for discussing American vs British English (EUCLID 2019, 27-35). I was brought up, have studied and lived all my life in countries that were former British colonies. My appreciation of American English is therefore relatively recent, amplified because most word processing packages set to default to American English. My top-of-mind experience with the difference between the two languages is having to confirm to my word processor that words like *organise* and *programme* are correctly spelt on the many occasions I am too lazy to switch the default language to British English. It appears that I have never had to strictly ensure that I am using one of these languages over the other so this is bound to be a challenge for me. The coursepack introduces a whole world of differences not just in spelling but also in choice of words, punctuation, grammar, syntax, pronunciation, and writing of dates. To say nothing of the differences in obscenities and implied obscenities (EUCLID 2019, 27-35). The chapter left me feeling dizzy with my meal not going as well as I had hoped.

7) QUOTATIONS AND QUOTATION MARKS

Quotations and quotation marks are discussed in both chapters two and eight of the coursepack (EUCLID 2019, 5- 13, 44- 55). In Chapter two quotations are defined and their usage and correct citation explained. Long quotations (over four lines of text) are distinguished from other types of quotations. EUCLID templates provide a style for long quotations which specifies the fonts, type of indentation and spacing to be used. In general, the use of multiple quotations in the same document is discouraged since it compromises originality. Chapter eight discusses the use of quotations as part of a broader discussion on use of the Chicago Style. In the EUCLID documents I have seen so far, the Chicago Style and Turabian Style are mentioned as though they are at the very least interchangeable or otherwise one and the same. I felt it was important to understand what the difference was if any. The University of Pittsburgh offered what I thought was a simple and straightforward clarification, “These styles [Turabian] are essentially the same as those presented in *The Chicago Manual of Style* with slight modifications for the needs of student writers”. I was also pleased with their clear presentation of the two citation documentation systems in the Turabian style which will be discussed further in the next section on referencing.

I was unaware that the Latin term *sic* frequently seen in journalistic writing is used to emphasize the unusual use of a concept word, term or phrase while reproducing a quote exactly as it was originally (EUCLID 2019, 48). Given the wide everyday usage of the word, I was embarrassed about having never bothered to find out what exactly it meant. From chapter eight I also learnt that quotation marks can be used outside a quote when a non-English word is being translated or to give special emphasis to a word that is wrongly used (EUCLID 2019, 47).

8) CITATION AND REFERENCING

Referencing is a prerequisite for all academic writing (EUCLID 2019, 4) providing the means through which the source of images, ideas, concepts, words, text, data, code and opinion among others are acknowledged (University of Kent). The relatively large number of available referencing styles can be broadly categorized into three groups, documentary note, parenthetical/author-date and numbered styles (Lund University). Most academic institutions will define the referencing style that the students should use. When I did my first graduate program, we used Harvard, an author-date referencing style for all our academic work. EUCLID recommends the use of the Turabian style (EUCLID 2019, 24) which according to the University of Pittsburgh, presents, “two basic documentation systems, notes-bibliography style (or simply bibliography style) and author-date style (previously called parenthetical citations–reference list style)”. Whichever style is used the in-text referencing [also known as citation] is linked to a list of works either a bibliography or a reference list (EUCLID 2019, 10). The material on citations and referencing is mentioned in bits and pieces in at least three chapters of the study guide. As such, despite going over it a number of times, I felt did not feel confident about correctly using the recommended style. I also noted some inconsistencies in use of the Turabian style within

the study material. A simple case in point is for in-text citations. The example on page II of the study material and those in the CMS Crib Sheet include year with comma separation however the page six explanation on in-text citations makes no mention of year.

9) CONCLUSION

I embarked on this first period of the first course with great trepidation. On the surface, the coursepack seemed to be a mish mash of rather disjointed topics and extracts brought together under one umbrella with no clear structure holding it all together. As I delved deeper, I found myself enjoying the opportunity to let go of my assumptions and prejudices; and open myself up to learning and relearning. In the end I felt like I had taken a trip back in time through all my different levels of education, kindergarten through graduate school. It has been a pleasurable experience that I would not hesitate to recommend to anyone else. As for the journey, I feel that the food provided has indeed given me that boost that I need to face the road ahead with courage.

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